

Effect of E-Learning Training Methods and Instructor Competencies on the Effectiveness of Training Mediated by Training Motivation

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine whether the instructor's competence affected the effectiveness of training, whether the e-learning training method affected training motivation, whether the instructor's competence affected training motivation, whether explanation involved the significance of movement, and whether the e-learning training method was mediated by training motivation affects the effectiveness of training, Does the competence of instructors mediated by training motivation affect the effectiveness of training, Does the competence of instructors affect employee e-learning training methods. The results showed that Instructor Competence had a positive and significant effect on training effectiveness. Instructor competence has a positive and significant impact on the training motivation using the E-Learning Training Method. Moreover, the E-Learning Training Method has a positive and significant effect on Training Motivation. Also, training motivation has a positive and significant impact on Training Effectiveness, and Instructor Competence has a positive and significant impact on Training Effectiveness through Training Motivation.

1. Introduction

Human Resource Development (HRD) is used to form globally competitive individuals. Human resource development can be started from the first time an individual enters a company or agency while in the agency until retirement. Human resource development can be done using training methods or commonly called training. The training program can be carried out indoors, namely in a room or outdoors or often called outbound, a training program through games with an emphasis on

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learning. Indoor training can be done with face-to-face training methods, e-learning or virtual learning, or face-to-face and e-learning known as blended learning. Based on the results of the pre-research, 29 employees participated in the training during the period 2020 to 2021. Eight employees participated in the e-learning method training, one person in blended learning and 20 face-to-face meetings. It can be concluded that there are still more employees who attend face-to-face training than e-learning even during the Covid 19 pandemic. Thus proving that employees are more interested in attending face-to-face training than e-learning.

Practical training is if the trainees can understand the content of the training material and apply their knowledge and skills in the real world (Lim et al., 2007). Based on the results of pre-research on employees who participated in the training from 2020 to 2021, the following data were obtained.

Table 1
Effectiveness of E-Learning Training Programs

No	Training Objective	Description			
		Not Enough	Average	Understand	Very Understand
1	Understanding of all training materials	1	1	3	3
2	Understanding of the main points in the training material	2	1	4	1
3	Understanding of the benefits of training materials for competency improvement	2	2	3	2
4	Understanding how to apply training materials to daily work	2	2	4	
5	Understanding how to convey training materials to other co-workers	3	1	3	1

Based on the results of pre-research from 8 employees who took part in training using the e-learning method, three employees who understand the entire material presented, the main points in the training material are one person, Regarding the benefits of training materials for competency improvement 2, no one understands how to apply training materials to their daily work, as well as how to deliver training materials to other co-workers as much as one person.

Table 2
Effectiveness of Face-to-face (Conventional) Training Programs

No	Training Objective	Description
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		Average	Understand	Very Understand
1	Understanding of the entire training material	3	8	9
2	Understanding of the main points in the training material	4	8	8
3	Understanding of the benefits of training materials for competency improvement	3	9	8
4	Understanding how to apply training materials to daily work	4	10	6
5	Understanding how to convey training materials to other co-workers	4	9	7

From the pre-research data recap, 20 employees took part in the face-to-face training, showing that they understood the overall material presented, amounting to 9 people, the main points in the training material were eight people, on the benefits of training materials for improving the competence of 8 people, very understanding of how to apply training materials into the daily work of 6 people, as well as how to convey training materials to other colleagues as many as seven people.

Table 3
Effectiveness of Blended Learning (Mixed) Training Program

No	Training Objective	Description		
		Average	Understand	Very Understand
1	Understanding of all training materials	1		
2	Understanding of the main points in the training material		1	
3	Understanding of the benefits of training materials for competency improvement		1	
4	Understanding how to apply training materials to daily work	1		
5	Understanding how to convey training materials to other co-workers	1		

From the pre-research data recap, one employee attended the blended learning training, showing that none of the employees understood the overall material presented. The main points in the training material amounted to the benefits of training materials for increasing competence, understanding how to apply training materials in daily work, and how to convey training materials to other colleagues.

Effective training is influenced by the training model used. In the era of the COVID-19 pandemic, e-learning training methods are widely used by companies or government agencies to improve the competence and performance of their employee's training, to reduce the spread of the COVID-19 virus due to crowds. In addition, the e-learning training model is considered more efficient because agencies or companies do not need to pay for transportation, accommodation, and consumption. Training is teaching employees the basic skills needed to carry out their duties. As for the old employees, the purpose of the training is to improve their poor performance by learning new knowledge and technology and skills and adapting to new organizational developments and policies. (Budhianto, 2020).

The e-learning method uses technology and communication to encourage participants to be more active in learning, which is not limited by distance or place. Another term for electronic learning is online learning, internet-enabled learning, virtual learning or web-based learning (Rahman et al., 2020).

So it can be concluded that e-learning method training is a process of teaching-related employees basic skills in carrying out tasks to improve performance by using electronic learning that is not limited by distance and place. E-learning methods are often considered as effective as face-to-face methods, with the interaction between instructors and participants being an important factor in the effectiveness of e-learning. An e-learning design that accommodates the interaction between instructors and participants and provides an opportunity to practice the material with simulations, if appropriately applied in work, can create e-learning effectiveness (Noesgaard & rngreen, 2015).

Kompas.com reports that increasing self-capacity by participating in various online training is attractive to workers. This can be seen from a site that provides business and creative videos, which tripled in April 2020. The most followed skills program was "Zoom" with an increase of more than 6,000 per cent and virtual jobs by 5,800 per cent. "Zoom" is one of the most frequently used media in online training (E-learning) (Lusia Kus Anna, 2020).

The training design (training method) will improve the trainees' ability, for example, training motivation (Tai, 2006). So if the training method using e-learning can be designed attractively, it can generate high interest (motivation) from participants to participate in the training. Based on the research related to the effectiveness of the training described above, it can be proposed that there are three factors in shaping the effectiveness of the training, namely (1) the E-learning Training Method, which is one of the training methods that can be applied during the covid 19 pandemic to develop competence employee. (2) Instructor Competence is one factor that encourages employees to be interested in participating in training. (3) Training motivation is one of the important factors for employees to achieve effective training. Thus, this research will focus on the three determination variables. This study proposes a research model by examining training motivation as an intervening variable that mediates the effect of e-learning training methods and instructor competencies on training effectiveness, as in the research conducted by Sitzmann, T., Brown, KG, Casper, WJ, Ely, K., & Zimmerman, R. D (2008) in his research A Review and Meta-Analysis of the Nomological Network of Trainee Reactions. This study explained that a good interaction process between the instructor and the trainees could result in greater motivation and a more positive attitude towards the learning and instructional process. In addition, according to the research of Keramati et al. (2011), the role of

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readiness factors in E-learning outcomes: An empirical study conducted by the participant-centred e-learning method, if participants are motivated and confident, then the implementation of e-learning gets good results.

The Ministry of Manpower's Central Technical Implementation Unit (UPTP) is located in 16 provinces in Indonesia. Researchers chose the island of Java as the research location because of the limited research time and the island that has the most UPTP. Based on the explanation above, this research was structured to look at the Effect of E-Learning Training Methods and Instructor Competence in Mediation by Training Motivation on Training Effectiveness.

2. Materials and Methods

The research method used is a descriptive method with a quantitative approach, namely research based on data that describes the characteristics of people, events or situations that involve quantitative data. This study is correlational, explaining the relationship between variables (Uma Sekaran, 2017). In this study, a descriptive method was used to analyze the effect of the E-Learning Training Method (X1) and Instructor Competence (X2), mediated by Training Motivation (Y) on Training Effectiveness (Z).

3. Results and Discussions

Influence of Instructor Competence on Training Effectiveness

Based on the hypothesis test results, the t-statistic value is greater than t table $2,271 > 1,960$, and the p-value is smaller than, i.e. $0.024 < 0.05$. These results identify a significant influence between Instructor Competence on Training Effectiveness. Then the path coefficient shows a positive original sample result of 0.152, which indicates a positive relationship between Instructor Competence and Training Effectiveness. So it can be concluded that there is a significant positive influence between Instructor Competence on the Effectiveness of Training for UPTP Kemnaker Employees in Java Island. Thus Hypothesis H1 is accepted.

The results of this study are in line with research (Johnson & Brown, 2017) (Lim et al., 2007), (Sari et al., 2017), (Yixi Wang et al., 2021), and (Siswanto et al., 2018) who also found that there was a positive influence between Instructor Competence on Training Effectiveness. The higher the level of Instructor Competence, the higher the training effectiveness achieved by employees. Vice versa, the lower the Instructor's Competence, the lower the Training Effectiveness achieved by employees. The results of hypothesis testing are strengthened by descriptive statistical results on the Instructor Competency and Training Effectiveness variables which show that the majority of respondents answered agree on both variables, with the average value of respondents' answers being at high intervals (4.03 average total on Instructor Competence and 4.02 Training Effectiveness). Most respondents feel that the better the Instructor's Competence in information technology knowledge and skills, the higher the effectiveness of employee training. Vice versa, the lack of instructor competence in technology and information knowledge and skills, the lower the effectiveness of employee training. This is in line with the opinion (Alariqi et al., 2019) that the instructor's lack of competence in information technology knowledge and skills significantly affects the effectiveness of the training.

The Influence of Instructor Competence on E-Learning Training Methods

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, which is indicated by the t-statistic value greater than t table $18,580 > 1.960$ and the p-value smaller than, i.e. $0.000 < 0.05$. These results identify a significant influence between Instructor Competencies on E-Learning Training Methods. Then the path coefficient shows a positive original sample result of 0.741, indicating a positive relationship between Instructor Competence and E-Learning Training Methods.

So it can be concluded that there is a significant positive effect between Instructor Competence on E-Learning Training Methods for UPTP Kemnaker Employees in Java Island. Thus, Hypothesis H2 is accepted. The results of this study are in line with research (Gulbahar, 2015), (Saad & Yamin, 2021), (Liaw & Chen, 2007) and (Almas et al., 2021), who also found that there was a positive influence on Instructor Competence on E-Learning Training Methods. The higher the level of Instructor Competence, the higher the use of the E-Learning Training Method. Vice versa, the lower the Instructor's Competence, the lower the use of the E-Learning Training Method. The results of hypothesis testing are strengthened by descriptive statistical results on the Instructor Competence and E-Learning Training Method variables which show that the majority of respondents answered agree on both variables with an average value. Respondents' answers were at high intervals (a total average of 4.03 on Instructor Competence and 4.04 for E-Learning Training Methods). Interaction with instructors has an important role in learning using e-learning methods. Instructor behaviour minimizes social and psychological distance with participants by using humour or by calling out participants' names and encouraging participant communication and feedback. This result corresponds to what was said (Johnson & Brown, 2017) that interaction with instructors has an important role in e-learning learning. Instructor behaviour that reduces social and psychological distance with participants positively impacts e-learning learning. Behaviours such as using humour, calling participants by name and encouraging student communication and feedback, that the instructor is available and willing to help them, and they are important to the instructor.

The Influence of Instructor Competence on Training Motivation

Based on the test results, the t-statistic value is greater than the t table, namely $5.989 > 1.960$ and the p-value $0.000 < 0.05$. These results identify a significant influence between Instructor Competence on Training Motivation. Then the path coefficient shows a positive original sample result of 0.330, indicating a positive relationship between Instructor Competence and Training Motivation. So it can be concluded that there is a significant positive influence between Instructor Competence on Training Motivation for UPTP Kemnaker Employees on Java Island. Thus Hypothesis H3 is accepted. The results of this study are in line with those (Aziz, 2016) and (Towler & Dipboye, 2006), who found that Instructor Competence had a significant positive effect on employee training motivation. The higher the level of Instructor Competence, the higher the Employee Training Motivation. Vice versa, the lower the Instructor's Competence, the lower the Employee Training Motivation.

The results of the hypothesis test were strengthened by the results of descriptive statistics on the Instructor Competency variable and the Training Motivation variable, which showed that the majority of respondents answered agreed on these two variables, with the average value of respondents' answers at high intervals (total average 4.03 on Instructor Competence and 4,11 on Training Motivation). Competent instructors can encourage trainees to learn better. This is following the statement (Budhianto, 2020) that competent instructors can encourage trainees to have a more positive attitude towards instructors so that participants will learn and practice better.

The Effect of E-Learning Training Methods on Training Effectiveness

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Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the t-statistic value is greater than the t table, namely $3.010 > 1.960$, and the p-value is smaller than, namely $0.003 < 0.05$. These results identify a significant effect between the E-Learning Training Method on the Effectiveness of the Training. Then the path coefficient shows a positive original sample result of 0.204, which indicates a positive relationship between the E-Learning Training Method and the Effectiveness of the Training. So it can be concluded that there is a significant positive effect between the E-Learning Training Method on the Effectiveness of Training for UPTP Kemnaker employees on Java Island. Thus Hypothesis H4 is accepted. The results of this study are in line with Chorra(2019), Richard D. Johnson and Kenneth G. Brown(2017)and(Lim et al., 2007), who found that the E-Learning Training Method had a significant positive effect on the effectiveness of employee training. The higher the use of the E-Learning Training Method, the higher the effectiveness of employee training. Vice versa, the lower the use of the E-Learning Training Method, the lower the effectiveness of employee training

The results of the hypothesis test are strengthened by descriptive statistical results on the E-Learning Training Method variable and the Training Effectiveness variable, which shows that the majority of respondents answered agree on both variables, with the average value of respondents' answers at high intervals (total average of 4.04 on the method). E-Learning Training and 4.03 on Training Effectiveness). The e-learning method is considered as effective as face-to-face through good interaction between the instructor and the trainees. Using the e-learning method, the instructor can practice the material using simulations so that participants can more easily receive training materials so that the effectiveness of the training can be achieved. This is in accordance with the statement(Noesgaard & rngreen, 2015)that the e-learning method is often considered to be as effective as the face-to-face method, with the interaction between the instructor and participants being an important factor in the effectiveness of e-learning. An e-learning design that accommodates the interaction between instructors and participants and provides an opportunity to practice the material with simulations, if appropriately applied in work, can create e-learning effectiveness.

The Effect of E-Learning Training Methods on Training Motivation

Based on the results of hypothesis testing (H5) at 4.21, the t-statistic value is greater than the t-table value, namely $11.497 > 1.960$, and the p-value is smaller than, i.e. $0.000 < 0.05$. These results identify that there is a significant influence between the E-Learning Training Method on Training Motivation. Then the path coefficient shows a positive original sample result of 0.614, which indicates that there is a positive relationship between the E-Learning Training Method and Training Motivation. So it can be concluded that there is a significant positive effect between the E-Learning Training Method on the Training Motivation of UPTP Kemnaker employees in Java. Thus Hypothesis H5 is accepted. The results of this study are in line with those (Aziz & Ahmad, 2011), (Hoerunnisa et al., 2019)and(Aziz, 2016)who found that the E-Learning Training Method had an effect on Training Motivation. The higher the use of the E-Learning Training Method, the higher the employee's training motivation. Vice versa, the lower the use of the E-Learning Training Method, the lower the employee's training motivation. The application of a good training model can improve the ability of participants. Among others, participants are more motivated to participate in the training (Tai, 2006).

The results of hypothesis testing are strengthened by descriptive statistical results on the E-Learning Training Method variable and the Training Motivation variable, which shows that the majority of respondents answered agree on both variables with the average value of respondents' answers at high intervals (total average of 4.04 in E-Learning Training Methods and 4.11 on Training Motivation).

Respondents, in this case, attended training using e-learning methods well with synchronous learning mechanisms (instructors interact directly) and indirectly (asynchronously) where the instructor interacts with the participants directly (synchronous) or indirectly (asynchronous). As said by (Rahman et al., 2020) that the e-learning learning mechanism can be done synchronously and asynchronously.

The Effect of Training Motivation on Training Effectiveness

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the value indicated by the t-statistic value is greater than t arithmetic, namely $9.012 > 1.960$, and the p-value is smaller than the value, namely $0.000 < 0.05$. These results identify that there is a significant influence between Training Motivation on Training Effectiveness. Then the path coefficient shows a positive original sample result of 0.594, which indicates that there is a positive relationship between Training Motivation and Training Effectiveness. So it can be concluded that there is a significant positive effect between Training Motivation on the Effectiveness of Training for UPTP Kemnaker employees on Java Island. Thus Hypothesis H6 is accepted. The results of this study are in line with Setyaningsih et al. (2020), Noesgaard & rngreen (2015), and Ibrahim et al. (2020), who found that Training Motivation had an effect on Training Effectiveness. The higher the training motivation, the higher the effectiveness of employee training. Vice versa, the lower the motivation for training, the lower the effectiveness of the training.

The results of hypothesis testing are strengthened by descriptive statistical values on the variables of Training Motivation and Training Effectiveness, which show that the majority of respondents answered agree on these variables, with the average value being in the high interval (average level of 4.11 on Training Motivation and 4.03 on Training Effectiveness). Respondents in this study showed a fairly high level of training motivation by following the training program properly and transferring the knowledge gained in the workplace so that the effectiveness of the training can be achieved. This is in line with what was conveyed (Tai, 2006) that motivation can influence a person to take part in a training program so that they will exert energy to follow the program and transfer what they have learned on the job, where motivation has a role in determining training performance.

Influence of Instructor Competence mediated by Training Motivation on Training Effectiveness

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the value indicated by the t-statistic value is greater than t arithmetic, namely $5.380 > 1.960$, and the p-value is smaller than the value, namely $0.000 < 0.05$. These results identify that there is a significant influence between Instructor Competence mediated by Training Motivation on Training Effectiveness. Then the path coefficient shows a positive original sample result of 0.196, which indicates that there is a positive relationship between the three variables, namely Competence, Training Motivation and Training Effectiveness. So it can be concluded that there is a significant positive effect between Instructor Competence mediated by Training Motivation on the Effectiveness of Training for UPTP Kemnaker employees in Java. Thus Hypothesis H7 is accepted. The results of this study are in line with those (Hodges, 2004) and (Sitzmann et al., 2008), who found that Instructor Competence had a significant indirect effect on Training Effectiveness mediated by Training Motivation. So it can be concluded that the higher the level of Instructor Competence, the higher the Training Motivation, which has an impact on the high Training Effectiveness.

This is also reinforced by the results of hypothesis testing H3 that there is a significant positive effect between Instructor Competence on Training Motivation and the H6 hypothesis that there is a

significant positive effect between Training Motivation on Employee Training Effectiveness. Thus, the results of statistical research show that Instructor Competence has a significant positive effect on Training Effectiveness when mediated by Training Motivation. The results of hypothesis testing are also reinforced by descriptive statistical results on the Instructor Competence, Training Motivation and Training Effectiveness variables which show that the majority of respondents answered agree on the three variables. The average values of respondents' answers in high intervals (a total average of 4.03 on Instructor Competence, 4.11 on Training Motivation and 4.03 on Training Effectiveness). Respondents in this study have the perception that the instructor's ability to interact with training participants can produce greater motivation so that the success of the learning process can create training effectiveness.

The Effect of E-Learning Training Methods mediated by Training Motivation on Training Effectiveness

Based on the results of hypothesis testing (H8) at 4.21, the value indicated by the t-statistic value is greater than t arithmetic, namely $6.708 > 1.960$, and the p-value is smaller than the value, which is $0.000 < 0.05$. These results identify that there is a significant effect between the E-Learning Training Method mediated by Training Motivation on Training Effectiveness. Then the path coefficient shows a positive original sample result of 0.365, which indicates that there is a positive relationship between the three variables, namely the E-Learning Training Method, Training Motivation and Training Effectiveness. So it can be concluded that there is a significant positive effect between the E-Learning Training Method mediated by Training Motivation on the Effectiveness of Training for UPTP Kemnaker employees in Java. (Ahmisuhaiti et al., 2016), (Kodwani & Prashar, 2019b), and (Cheng et al., 2012) found that the E-Learning Training Method had a significant indirect effect on the Effectiveness of Training mediated by Training Motivation. So it can be concluded that the higher the use of the E-Learning Training Method, the higher the Training Motivation, which has an impact on the high effectiveness of the training. This is also reinforced by the results of hypothesis testing H5 that there is a significant positive effect between the E-Learning Training Method on Training Motivation and the H6 hypothesis that there is a significant positive effect between Training Motivation on the Effectiveness of Employee Training. Thus, the results of statistical research show that the E-Learning Training Method has a significant positive effect on Training Effectiveness when mediated by Training Motivation.

The results of the hypothesis test are also strengthened by descriptive statistical results on the variables of the E-Learning Training Method, Training Motivation and Training Effectiveness which shows the majority of respondents answered agree on these three variables, with the average values of respondents' answers being in high intervals (total average 4.04 on E-Learning Training Methods, 4.11 on Training Motivation and 4.03 on Training Effectiveness). Respondents in this study have the perception that the instructor's ability to interact with training participants can produce greater motivation so that the success of the learning process can create training effectiveness. Employees feel that the application of the training method with participant-centred E-Learning can motivate participants so that the level of success (effectiveness) in training can be achieved. According to Keramati et al. (2011), The e-learning method is participant-centred. If the participants are motivated and confident, then the implementation of e-learning gets good results.

4. Conclusion

In accordance with the research that has been carried out and the discussion on the effect of the E-Learning Training Method and Instructor Competence mediated by Training Motivation on the

Effectiveness of Training at the UPTP Kemnaker Java Island, the researchers obtained the following conclusions:

1. The E-Learning Training Method has a positive and significant effect on Training Motivation. The higher the use of the E-Learning Training Method, the higher the level of Training Motivation possessed. UPTP Kemnaker employees in Java Island.
2. Training motivation has a positive and significant effect on the effectiveness of training. The higher the training motivation, the higher the effectiveness of the training achieved by the employees of the UPTP Kemnaker Java Island.
3. Instructor Competence has a positive and significant effect on the effectiveness of training through training motivation for employees of UPTP Kemnaker Java Island. The higher the level of Instructor Competence, the higher the Training Motivation, which has an impact on the higher the level of Training Effectiveness achieved by the employees of the UPTP Kemnaker Java Island.
4. The E-Learning Training Method has a positive and significant effect on the effectiveness of training through the motivation of training for employees of the UPTP Kemnaker Java Island. The higher the use of the E-Learning Training Method, the higher the level of Employee Motivation which has an impact on the higher the level of Training Effectiveness achieved by the employees of the UPTP Kemnaker Java Island.
5. The E-Learning Training Method has a positive and significant effect on Training Motivation. The higher the use of the E-Learning Training Method, the higher the level of Training Motivation possessed. UPTP Kemnaker employees in Java Island.
6. Training motivation has a positive and significant effect on the effectiveness of training. The higher the training motivation, the higher the effectiveness of the training achieved by the employees of the UPTP Kemnaker Java Island.
7. Instructor Competence has a positive and significant effect on the effectiveness of training through training motivation for employees of UPTP Kemnaker Java Island. The higher the level of Instructor Competence, the higher the Training Motivation, which has an impact on the higher the level of Training Effectiveness achieved by the employees of the UPTP Kemnaker Java Island.
8. The E-Learning Training Method has a positive and significant effect on the effectiveness of training through the motivation of training for employees of the UPTP Kemnaker Java Island. The higher the use of the E-Learning Training Method, the higher the level of Employee Motivation which has an impact on the higher the level of Training Effectiveness achieved by the employees of the UPTP Kemnaker Java Island.

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